

TESTING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES USING MOIRE INTERFEROMETRY

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ABSTRACT

Until now high-sensitivity moire interferometry was used almost exclusively at room temperature. Previous attempts at extending the temperature range for this experimental method have had limited success. Their complexity, cost and limitations prohibited these developments from being widely used. A new approach of performing the measurements in a vacuum oven using an achromatic interferometer is presented in this paper. Experimental results of measurements of deformation on the edge of a composite coupon subjected to the elevated temperature are demonstrated. Work on further increasing the temperature range for the application to ceramics and ceramic matrix composites is in progress.

KEYWORDS: Composites; High temperatures; Moire; Interferometry; Deformation

1. INTRODUCTION

High-sensitivity moire interferometry is a method of precisely measuring the deformation of solid bodies under various loading conditions. It is a full-field technique that can be classified as a combination of holography and the traditional moire method. It maintains all the sensitivity of holography and at the same time offers the easy to interpret interferograms typical for moire methods. The contrast of the patterns is usually better than in either one of the parent techniques.

High-sensitivity moire interferometry was introduced by Guild in 1956 as a powerful experimental method of measuring deformations of solid bodies [1]. It extended the sensitivity of traditional moire interferometry by two orders of magnitude. Since then a wide range of materials has been tested by moire interferometry including simple isotropic materials and exotic high-performance composites. Virtually all experiments described in the literature, however,

have been performed at room temperature. Some attempts at making unidirectional measurements have been made in the past, but the instability of the systems used, the high cost and the complexity of the experimental work at a very limited temperature range prohibited these procedures from being widely used.

Under the sponsorship of CIT and duPont, work has been done to extend the range of applications of moire interferometry to high-temperature regimes. At the lower temperature range, applicable to polymers, this work was also co-sponsored by the NSF Science and Technology center. A new moire interferometer was developed for bidirectional measurements in a vacuum oven. The system has been successfully tested at both room at elevated temperatures.

2. MOIRE INTERFEROMETRY

Moire interferometry is an optical measuring technique based on two-beam interference. Figure 1 illustrates the basic principle of a moire interferometry system. Two collimated and mutually coherent beams of light, A and B, illuminate a diffraction grating produced on a flat surface of a specimen. This specimen grating follows the deformation of the specimen surface and modulates the shape of the wavefronts of the diffracted beams. A', the first diffraction order of illuminating beam A and B', the minus-first diffraction order of the other illuminating beam interfere, producing an interference fringe pattern recorded on the camera back.

Figure 1 Basic moire interferometry system.

If the interferometer is tuned properly at the initial no-load, configuration the two diffracted beams emerge along the normal to the specimen surface and the pattern produced is a uniform intensity field called a null field. After a load is applied the specimen deforms, and the new pattern is a contour map of the phase difference of the two interfering beams. The fringes are assigned numbers called fringe-orders, defined by Equation (1). Since a fringe order is directly proportional to the in-plane displacements of the points of the specimen surface in the direction perpendicular to the grating lines, the new fringe pattern is a contour-map of the component of the displacement field in the same direction.

$$N = \frac{S}{\lambda} + C \quad (1)$$

where N is the fringe order

S is the phase difference

λ is the wave-length of light

C is a constant corresponding to rigid body motion

Equation (2) defines the relationship between the fringe-order and the displacement it represents for the case presented above.

$$U = \frac{N}{2 f_s} \quad (2)$$

where U is the displacement

f_s is the frequency of the specimen grating

There are numerous ways to implement the basic idea of moire interferometry. Usually, a collimated beam of coherent light is divided into two or four parts and directed toward the specimen grating at the proper angles. The whole system is built on a large and heavy holographic table insulated from vibrations. In these laboratory systems motion of any optical element affects the results. The presence of a hot body in the vicinity of such a system could introduce unacceptable and inestimable errors.

3. HIGH-TEMPERATURE MOIRE INTERFEROMETER

The achromatic interferometer [2] developed for use in a materials-testing laboratory environment is much more resistant to both vibrations and thermal air currents. For this reason it was chosen for the high temperature work. It was modified so the distance between the specimen and the optics could be maximized and the compactness of the configuration preserved.

The new design is schematically illustrated in Figure 2. A collimated beam illuminates a diffraction grating at normal incidence. Its first and minus-first diffraction orders are directed by a system of four mirrors so they illuminate the specimen grating at precisely defined angles.

One of the mirrors, indicated in the diagram by letter D, can be adjusted, allowing the instrument to be fine tuned. High-precision electric actuators are used to provide a way for remote control when the interferometer is positioned in a vacuum oven. At higher temperatures a vacuum will be necessary to protect the instrument from thermal deformation and prevent the motion of the interference fringes associated with air currents. The small sensitivity to the movement of the illuminating beam allowed the laser and the collimating optics to be positioned outside of the chamber, thereby reducing the requirements for the size of the oven.

Figure 2. Moire interferometer for high temperature applications. Remote control of the adjusting screws allows the instrument to be positioned in a vacuum oven.

To obtain all three components of the two-dimensional strain tensor it is necessary to measure two orthogonal components of the in-plane displacement field. To achieve this goal, two systems were built on a common frame, creating a stable and compact instrument. A total of four remotely controlled actuators were used to control the system. Their configuration allows not only fine tuning of the interferometer to eliminate the initial field, but also rigid-body rotation of the whole instrument with respect to the specimen. This is useful in introducing a carrier pattern of rotation, which can be used in a high-resolution analysis of deformation of the specimen.

The interferometer is positioned in a vacuum oven that was designed and built specifically for this purpose. It is constructed out of two large diameter (450 mm) steel pipes welded together to form a T. This configuration minimizes the volume of the space that must be handled by the vacuum pump and at the same time provides a relatively large useful space for the specimen and the loading frame. The specimen compartment is 750 mm high. Both of its ends are closed by removable plates that allow easy access to the specimen and fixturing. The

whole apparatus is mounted to a steel frame suspended on four air mounts and stabilized by precision leveling valves.

The temperature of the interferometer and the specimen are measured by a number of thermocouples connected to a data acquisition system based on a Macintosh personal computer. The data acquisition board that is used also allows control of the heaters, if such an option is necessary in some future application, for example a long-duration creep test.

4. DEFORMATION OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY COUPON SUBJECTED TO HIGH TEMPERATURE

The first experiment was performed in order to test this new instrument experimentally. A high-frequency diffraction grating was replicated on the edge of a graphite/epoxy composite coupon, with a stacking sequence of $[0_2/60_2/-60_2]_s$. The specimen was attached to a resistance heater and positioned in front of the interferometer. No mechanical load was applied to the specimen. The patterns were recorded every 40°C up to 180°C (356°F). For clarity, the pattern was modified by a low-frequency carrier pattern. Figure 3 demonstrates the deformation during the heating process and Figure 4 during cooling.

The shape of the fringes in this pattern is characteristic of the edge effect in this ply configuration. It can be noticed that between 140°C and 180°C the material passed through the glass transition temperature and some residual stresses were released, causing a sudden increase in the deformation. During the cooling stage the pattern became slightly irregular. These fringe irregularities can be attributed to the nonuniform deformation of the specimen on the micro-scale due to the nonuniform distribution of fibers within the plies.

In spite of the fact that the experiment was performed under atmospheric pressure, the quality of the results is very good. The test was performed at the standard sensitivity of 417 nm per fringe order, and the pattern demonstrated good spatial resolution. Due to the small dimensions of the specimen, thermal air currents did not pose a problem.

In the future all high-temperature work will be performed in a vacuum. It is expected that the vacuum environment should permit measurements at much higher temperatures, while at the same time assuring a more uniform temperature distribution. The long-term goal is 1000°C, corresponding to the conditions seen by ceramics and ceramic-matrix composites.

Figure 3. Horizontal displacement field due to thermal deformation of the edge of a graphite/epoxy composite coupon heated from room temperature to 180°C.

Figure 4. Horizontal displacement field due to thermal deformation of the edge of a graphite/epoxy composite coupon cooled from 180°C to room temperature.

5. HIGH-TEMPERATURE SPECIMEN GRATING

Before any measurement can be done using moire interferometry the specimen must be prepared by producing a diffraction grating on its surface. The standard procedure of specimen preparation is the replication of gratings from special molds. These molds are phase diffraction gratings treated with a parting substance and evaporated with a thin metallic layer. The mold is cemented to the specimen surface with a two-component adhesive and pulled away after the adhesive is cured. The thin metallic layer remains on the surface of the specimen, providing high reflectivity to the molded grating. When epoxy resin and aluminum coating are used, such a specimen grating can survive temperatures ranging up to about 220°C, which is sufficient for most applications to polymer matrix composites. Work is in progress on developing a replication procedure for a new family of high-temperature polymer matrix composites that can be used at temperatures as high as 450°C.

Since the long-range goal of this project is to provide the capability to test various materials at temperatures as high as 1000°C, a new method of specimen grating preparation was necessary. A procedure similar to the one used in the micro-chip industry was chosen. Preliminary work done under the sponsorship of DARPA indicated that this would be successful.

A high-temperature grating is produced by etching a thin metallic layer through a photoresist mask. First the surface of the specimen must be polished so its roughness is of the same order as the wave-length of the used light or better. The specimen is then cleaned and degreased using solvents, and positioned in a vacuum chamber where it is cleaned with an ion beam and then coated with a thin layer of gold by evaporation. After it is removed from the vacuum chamber, a thin layer of photoresist is applied to the surface.

The specimen is then positioned in an interferometer that produces a so-called virtual grating. The frequency of this "grating" was chosen to be 600 lines per millimeter. When the photoresist is exposed and developed it creates a mask consisting of thin, parallel and uniformly distributed strips. At this point the specimen is ready for plasma etching. It is positioned in the vacuum chamber which is then filled with oxygen at a pressure of the order of one millitor. The plasma source is activated and the specimen is etched for a few minutes. The quality of the grating is examined under a microscope and the etching is repeated if necessary. Once the result is satisfactory the photoresist is washed out and the remaining gold strips become an amplitude diffraction grating.

This experiment was performed on a block of silicon-carbide ceramic. The high temperature diffraction grating was tested for survivability and diffraction at elevated temperatures. The specimen was positioned in a furnace and heated in 100°C increments to the temperature of 1100°C. At each temperature level the grating was illuminated with a laser beam and a diffracted beam was observed on a screen. No deterioration of the grating was noticed

and the diffraction was good at all the temperature levels, indicating that moire measurements can be performed at these temperatures.

6. CURRENT AND FUTURE WORK

At present measurements are being done on composite specimens at temperatures ranging from 22°C to 200°C. The whole system is working in a vacuum and patterns have been observed. The interferometer described above was slightly modified in order to eliminate noise in the form of "ghost patterns" observed during the initial tests. A high-temperature fixture is being designed for a ceramic specimen. It is expected that measurements at the temperatures above 1000°C will be performed on this specimen by the end of the summer of 1991 under the continuing sponsorship of du Pont.

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